

NetLogo Model For Climate Change

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Abstract : Climate change model that observe the earth temperature. The earth temperature is modeled after earth's energy budget. In this model there are four parameters that divided into two category the geographical parameter and climate parameters. The geographical parameters are sun intensity and albedo while the climate parameters are cloud and CO² gas. From the simulation a steady increase of the CO² gas makes the earth warmer, an increase of 0.01 CO² gas per tick with initial value of 10 will make the temprature 16° C warmer after 45000 ticks. The lowest temprature of 26.78° C is given by setting the model with no CO² gas presence and a presence of 20 cloud while the highest temprature of 46.41° C is given by setting the model with a presence of 100 CO² gas and no cloud. After running simulation for 5 cycle of day/night with a frequency of day/night every 10000 tick with no change in parametes give no increase of temprature. A presence of CO² gas will make the night hotter since the earth will need more time to relase the heat.

Keywords : NetLogo, Climate Change

introduction

Earth had stood for 4.543 billion years and it has suffer many disaster that almost wipe out living organism. Many of this disasater are natural disaster such us volcano eruption like toba eruption that create volcanic winter¹. This volcanic winter that being created by the ashes that was blown into the atmospere obscure the sun. This volcanic ash in the atmospere made the earth cooler. Cooler earth temprature made growing crops unsuitable. Since most living organism need crops to survive, the lack of crops will led to starvation and eventualy death.

Global Land and Ocean Temperature Departure from 20th Century Average, January-October

Fig 1 : Global Land Ocean Temperature Departure From of the 20th Century Average

Nowdays human face the same problem but instead of cooling our proble revolve on heating. In the last 100 years there is an incerase of average daily temprature. The increase of temprature coralete with the increase of CO² gas in the atmosphere. This data is backed by finding carbon content that being trap on

ice, and the depth of the carbon content that being burried in the ice coralated with the number of years it was ciruclated.

Fig 2 : CO² and Earth Temperature Correlation

Method

In this paper we will explain what factor contribute to the increase of the temprature and run a model of it. The factor consist of geographic factor (Albedo and sun intensity) and climate factor (Cloud and CO² Gas. While the earth temprature was modeled after earth's energy budget².

In earth energy budget model explain that the sun rays that come to the earth are absorbed while others are refelcted back into the sky. The sun rays that being absorbed will increase the earth temprature. With the incerease or the temprature the earth also will radiated the heat into the sky as a long wave radiation (InfraRed). Since there is an absorbance and emittance of the heat therfore the earth will achive an equilibrium state where the earth will not turn cooler or warmer.

Fig 3 : Incoming Sung light Model

Fig 4 : IR Emission From The Earth

A CO_2 gas in the atmosphere will make the earth warmer. This phenomena was caused by the infrared emission from the earth was met with CO_2 gas. This interaction made the infrared bounce back into the earth. Since the energy that suppose to go into the sky was being reflected back in the the ground therefore will increase the earth temprature. This phemomane was called the green house effect.

Fig 5 : CO_2 Interation

There are two geographical factor for the simulation. The Sun brightness depends on geographical location, earth's orbit and the day/night cycle of the earth (earth orbit). The range value for this simaltion start from 0 that means no sunlight and 5 the sunlight in the equator.

Fig 6 : Geographical Sun Brightness

The albedo is the refletiveness of the surface. This also depends on the geographical location. White surface (white tile) have a higher albedo than black surface (asphalt). This mean that snow refleckt more sunlight that asphalt therefore if both are give a same intensity the asphalt will felt warmer than the white tile. The albedo in this simulation have range from 0 that means no absorbance and 1 that means no refelction.

Fig 6 : Earth Alebedo

The gathering of the cloud in the skt will make sun rays harder to penetrate since the light will be reflected (cloud has a high albedo). This can make the earth cooler since no sunlight will hit the ground and increase the earth's energy.

Fig 7 : Cloud Interaction With Sunlight

In this simulation the sun rays was being represented by the yellow beam (yellow agent) that come from the sky, the CO2 gas was being represented by the green agent and the heat was being represented by the red agent bellow the surface and the infrared emission was being represented by the red colour agent.

Fig 7 : Agent In NetLogo

The temperature for the next tick is increasing /decreasing with the number of heat agent with that follow this equation.

$$Temperature_{t+1} = (Temperature_t \times 0.99) + (0.01 \times (12 + \frac{Number\ of\ Heat\ agent}{10}))$$

The rate of the heat agent turn into IR agent have a chance 0 if the temperature is under 20° C and 1 if the temperature is over 60° C. While chance of the heat agent turn into IR agent in 20° C and 60° C is given by random number and gets higher chance with the increase of temperature.

$$Chance_{IR} = \frac{20 - Temperature}{40}$$

RESULT

After running the simulation for 45000 ticks with a steady increase of 0.002 CO² agent per tick that being rounded into integer give a temprature difference as being shown in figure 8.

Fig 8 : Steady Increase of Temperature

The red graph is the steady increase of CO² with the initial value of 10 and ended in 100. The blue graph show the increase of temprature if the CO² increase

while the orange graph show if there is no increase of temperature.

Running the simulation for different parameter such as:

1. Presence of cloud with no CO²
2. Presence of cloud with CO²
3. No Presence of cloud with CO²
4. No Presence of cloud with no CO²

The presence of cloud for this parameter have a value of 20 and the presence of CO² have a value of 100.

Fig 9 : Temperature with different parameter

The dotted blue graph show the temperature with parameters of no cloud and CO² this give average temperature of 30.36° C. The dotted gray graph show the temperature with parameters of no cloud and with CO² this give average temperature of 46.41° C. The continuous magenta graph show the temperature with parameters presence of cloud and no CO² this give average temperature of 26.78° C. The continuous orange graph show the temperature with parameters of presence of cloud and with CO² this give average temperature of 37.26° C.

Simulating the day/night cycle for every 10000 ticks that lasted for 45000 ticks with no change in the parameters. The parameters that makes the day/night cycle is the sun brightness that peak at the noon or 0.25 of the cycle while 0.5 to 1.0 of the cycle the sun brightness is 0 to simulate the night.

Fig 10 : Temperature with day/night cycle

The continuous black graph shown the sun intensity. The dotted blue graph show the temperature with

parameters of no cloud and no CO². The dotted gray graph show the temperature with parameters of no cloud and with CO². The continuous magenta graph show the temperature with parameters presence of cloud and no CO². The continuous orange graph show the temperature with parameters of presence of cloud and with CO².

CONCLUSION

Based on for the 3 simulation we can take conclusion as follows :

1. The increase of CO² will make the earth temperature warmer.
2. The increase of CO² with iniatial value of 10 and ended in 100 after 45000 ticks give a temperature difference of 16° C.
3. The lowest temprature of 26.78° C is achived by setting the parameters with Presence of cloud and with no CO².
4. highest temprature of 46.41° C is achived by setting the parameters with no Presence of cloud and with presence of CO².
5. Simulating the day/night cycle with no change in parameters give no increase of the temprature on the nexy day.
6. The presence of CO² gas makes releasing the heat is not efficient compared with no presence of CO², therefore it will make the night feels warmer.

REFERENCE

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